

Social Extension of Womenfolk in Delinquency Ethos; A Sociological Study

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Abstract

As nature of human, individuals want to test limitations that set by others. On the other hand, individual wants to fulfil their needs, material and spiritual, and desire to know about hidden things. It is true to all human beings. But it is different from person to person as well as from adult to child. Children's minds are hungry for knowledge and information, on one hand, it is their interest to know hidden things.

Key Words: Juveniles, Deviant Behavior, Law, Adults, Social Problems, Urbanization.

Introduction

On the other, they want to test curiosity in their social environment. So, by doing those acts they learn hide things and test limitations. They may commit or perform odd acts. Children are becoming abnormal person when they perform some act that can't be accepted by the adults and law. So, we can call the abnormal person "juvenile delinquency" for children. There are two types of delinquents, some delinquents are opposite of the adult wish, and some are opposite of the law in the society. In this research, researcher has studied causes of juvenile delinquency that they have caught by police. It can be defined juvenile delinquency as illegal acts which are committed by youth under the age of 18. Such acts are called delinquent behaviors. There are several causes behind the juvenile delinquency. The juveniles are the products of the defective families, the low economy and education, physiological and biological.

Social & Psychological Overview of Juvenile Delinquency

Juvenile delinquency is one of the serious problems of the mess society. It is almost an out-come of rapid urbanization and industrialization of modern times. Social conditions associated with two processes have affected the family pattern. This resulted in an atmosphere that is favorable to the growth of juvenile delinquency. Many children moving from rural areas to the cities or living in slums in cities are found to be highly vulnerable to this process. This has almost become a universal problem in most of the industrialized countries including India. Mr. G.C Dutt observes, "Juvenile delinquency is rapidly becoming a serious menace in India and with the progressive industrialization of many parts of country. This problem will soon assume the same proportions as in

many of the western. To understanding juvenile delinquency, we should know the meaning of both words. So here, I will try to demonstrate each concept in different views that readers can understand the concepts easily and clearly. However, there are many definitions for juvenile delinquency that each field of study defines it by their own view.

Delinquency is a kind of abnormality. When an individual deviates from the course of normal social life, his behavior is called "delinquency". When a juvenile, below an age specified under a statue exhibits which may prove to be dangerous to society and/or to him he may be called a 'juvenile delinquency'. Each state has its own precise definition of the age range covered by the word 'juvenile'.

The term 'Juvenile' means child and delinquent means criminal. Juvenile delinquency means crime committed by child. The term delinquency has been derived from the Latin word *delinquer*, which means 'to omit'. The Romans used the term to refer to the failure of a person to perform the assigned task or duty.

Differing from the legal definition of the controversial term, psychologists lay much emphasis upon the cause of juvenile delinquency in defining it. From legal viewpoint all those who are not apprehend are not criminals but from the psychological viewpoint all such offenders are also criminals. Consequently, the psychological definition of juvenile delinquency is more comprehensive than its legal definition. According to the psychologists, any, and every child, or either sex, between the ages of 15 to 18, who commits a crime, irrespective of the fact that he apprehended or not is a juvenile delinquent.

Community Focus of Juvenile Delinquency

To define juvenile delinquency according to social view, we must define deviance because according to sociologists' juvenile delinquency is social deviant. But there is no absolute way of defining a deviant act. Deviance can only be defined in relation to a particular standard and no standards are fixed or absolute. As such what is regarded as deviant varies from time to time and place to place. Society an act which is considered deviant today may be defined as normal in the future. An act defined as deviant in one society may be seen as perfectly normal in another. Put another way, deviance is culturally determined and cultural changed over time and vary from society to society. Sociologists define deviance as behavior that is recognized as violating expected rules and norms. Deviance is more than

simple nonconformity: it is behavior that departs significantly from social expectations. Sociologists distinguish two types of deviance: formal and informal. Formal deviance is behavior that breaks laws or official rules. Crime is an example. There are formal sanctions against formal deviance, such as imprisonment and fines. Informal deviance is behavior that violates customary norms. Unlike the public sociologists use the term deviance nonjudgmentally, to refer to any act to which people respond negatively. When sociologists use this term, it does not mean that they agree that an act is bad, just that people judge it negatively. To sociologists, then, all of us are deviants of one sort or another, for we all violate norms from time to time.

Ancient Setting of Juvenile Justice in the World

With the development of society, many new social problems and phenomena occur. Juvenile delinquency is one of them. To treat and solve them, there have been different discussions. Youth crime is a serious problem for society in past and present. In addition, day by day the youth crimes are increasing. If we want to understand the reasons of increasing youth crime and emerging of the issue, we should go back to history. It would be impossible to understand the topic of juvenile delinquency without first becoming familiar with the historical underpinnings which gave rise to the term juvenile delinquency. In the history administration of criminal justice, among the

early attempts to give differential treatment to persons of tender years, mention may be made of the 10th century monarch. King Athelstan of England, who enacted a law that "man shall not slay none younger than a fifteen winters' man." Overall, however, a juvenile who had committed an offense was dealt with as an ordinary criminal, and it is not surprising that in the 18th and 19th centuries, when the prevailing criminological theories favored the imprisonment of offenders, juveniles as well as adults were imprisoned. Statuses and the behavior expectations related to age are power social forces in every society and have created many ideals of childhood and young adulthood that are in constant conflict with dynamic changes from the rapid modernization of the last two centuries. Almost universally, children are different from adult and require special kinds of care and treatment. In fact, our current concept of childhood grew out of fertile philosophical debates in Europe during the Enlightenment. **Understanding the Social Thinkers perspectives towards the Delinquent Behavior**

The delinquency is of different types. As individual delinquency, group supported delinquency, organized delinquency, and situational delinquency. The researcher speaks about the causes of the delinquencies in societies. There are several causes for delinquencies like social cause, family cause, which leads them deviate. To understand the juveniles and the situations by which they deviate. The researcher fined the delinquency in individuals and groups and sometimes situations create the delinquent behavior. The contribution of the different thinkers like Ved Kumari sorts the work on the juvenile justice system. The juvenile justice system exists in India since the British rule. The acts were made for the children's deviant behavior, but the juveniles did not understand the punishment according to their deviant behavior, instead of the prisons the juveniles were send to the rehabilitation centers.

The social thinkers as if Larry J. Siegel and Brandon welsh are of the view that destruction of socio-cultural areas lead the deviance much. The unequal distribution of production probably was there the population is inversely proportionate as slum areas. The poverty and the minority stigmatized the

youth, and their minds keep on thinking about the revenge to society, as Deviation. The youth mostly the boys keep on thinking while they face the discrimination from the society. Finally, they came up with the gangs from their areas.

Conclusion

To summaries the research like this is not an easy task. The researcher also found so many limitations which became the hurdle for the researcher, moreover, the researcher come out with the fine data and clear picture about the juvenile delinquents and the rehabilitation centers and the pity law for the juveniles. The lack of some knowledge in this research may lead the other researcher to find something obvious as compared with the early works. The study of causes of juvenile delinquency is a part of social deviant as well as criminology. To understand and find out of juvenile delinquency is needed time and hard work especially in other society or country, because every society has different culture and law. They have own way to deal with their social problems. Also, the causes of the social problems are different form society to society. Even there are some similarities between some societies in general. As mentioned, it is not easy to study or do research in other society because it will take time and face on many limitations such as language and misunderstand of people. Juvenile delinquency is mean an abnormal act or crime that commit by a child who his/her age fewer than 18 in general. In most society the limited age of juvenile is 18 years. Delinquency contains all behavior that opposite with norms and legal. It means not only

crime belong delinquent but some abnormal behavior such as stay outside, truancy. In other hand such behaviors are not accepted by older people or parents. Even some behavior is normal for adults but is not normal for children such as smoking, drinking, truancy, etc. All delinquent behaviors, illegal and abnormal, have own causes that they commit by children. But there are different causes to create delinquent behaviors that they are different from person to person as well as from society to society. In

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